

Mohamed Hamdi KAANICHE

Tunis, Tunisia

+216 52 775 511 [✉ mhkaaniche@gmail.com](mailto:mhkaaniche@gmail.com)

[in linkedin.com/in/mhkaaniche](https://www.linkedin.com/in/mhkaaniche) [id orcid.org/0009-0008-5227-8756](https://orcid.org/0009-0008-5227-8756)

[U MQL5 Community Profile](#)

PROFESSIONAL PROFILE

Independent quantitative researcher with a hybrid background in experimental materials science (MRes, CNRS) and a decade of hands-on algorithmic trading systems development (MQL5). Focused on bridging practical market experience with rigorous research to design novel data architectures and methodologies for financial markets. Expertise lies in deconstructing complex systems and implementing robust, data-driven solutions.

RESEARCH & ACADEMIC OUTPUT

- **Master's Thesis:** *Physicochemical Characterization of Gene Delivery Vectors*. INSAT & CNRS UMR 6521.
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18418873](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18418873)
- **Bachelor's Thesis:** *Study of the Action of Polymeric Additives on Lubricating Oils*. FSS & SNDP.
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18419595](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18419595)
- **Technical Report:** *Standardized Protocols for Physicochemical Characterization of Liposomes*. CNRS UMR 6521.
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18419337](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18419337)
- **Full archive available via ORCID** ([0009-0008-5227-8756](https://orcid.org/0009-0008-5227-8756))

EXPERIENCE

Independent Quantitative Researcher Mar 2023 – Present
Tunis, Tunisia (Remote) *Self-Employed*

- Conducting independent research at the intersection of quantitative finance and data systems engineering.
- Focus on methodologies to improve accessibility, normalization, and analytical utility of financial market data for AI-driven analysis.
- Research interests: Financial data normalization architectures, API design, systematic market data analysis.

Lead Algorithmic Trading Systems Developer & Independent Researcher Jan 2013 – Mar 2022

Tunis, Tunisia (Hybrid) *Self-Employed*

- A decade of R&D in algorithmic trading: architecting multi-strategy Expert Advisors (MQL5), designing back-testing frameworks, managing an R&D lab.
- Deep, practical insight into market microstructure, data challenges, and system performance.
- Empirical foundation for current research in financial data infrastructure.

Master's Research Intern Jan 2012 – May 2012
CNRS UMR 6521, Brest, France

- Experimental research in nanomedicine: characterization of organophosphorus vectors for gene delivery.
- Techniques: Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), fluorescence spectroscopy, dynamic light scattering.

EDUCATION

INSAT - Institut National des Sciences Appliquées et de Technologie Sep 2010 – Jun 2012
Tunis, Tunisia *Master of Research, Industrial Chemistry*

- Thesis: *Physicochemical Characterization of Gene Delivery Vectors* (in partnership with CNRS).

- Grade: Distinction.

Faculté des Sciences de Sfax, University of Sfax
Sfax, Tunisia

Sep 2008 – Jun 2010
Bachelor's Degree, Industrial Chemistry

- Final Project: *Study of Polymeric Additives in Lubricating Oils* (with SNDP/AGIL Tunisia).
- Grade: Distinction.

Coding Dojo

U.S. Professional Certificates

Feb 2023 – May 2024
Computer Software Engineering

- Full-stack development certificates: Spring Boot, Django, React, MySQL, REST API.

TECHNICAL SKILLS

- **Quantitative Finance:** Algorithmic Trading, Market Microstructure, Financial Data Engineering.
- **Programming & Tech:** Python, MQL5, API Design, System Architecture, Data Analysis.
- **Research:** Methodological Design, Data Modeling, Academic Writing, Technical Documentation.
- **Languages:** French (Native), English (Professional), Arabic (Native).

Curriculum Vitae version 1.0. This document has a permanent DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18421929](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18421929) • Updated: January 29, 2026